

اقبال کی نظم ”طلوع اسلام“ احیائے اسلامی کی نوید

A HOPE FOR THE REVIVAL OF ISLAM: AN ANYLISIS OF IQBAL'S POEM "TULU-E-ISLAM"**Ammara Tariq (ORCID ID: 0000-0001-6198-6932)**

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ABSTRACT

Allam an Iqbal was one of those rare geniuses whose exceptional thoughts & excellence in the field of poetry has inspired our literature, politics, culture, economics and society. Basic message of Iqbal's poetry was of self-confidence, Muslim brotherhood and continuous progress in the collective consciousness of people & humanity.

Below referred research article envisage on Iqbal's important & long poem "Tulu-e-Islam" through which Iqbal exhibited optimism towards Muslim community and described that time of deep slumber will soon be ended. His further hope that his strong wish of Renaissance of Islam will be possible now as world-wide brotherhood & abundance of love is the secret of Islam. Muslim are creation who will be the builder of the world when they truly turn out to be the spokesman of God.

This research paper is aimed to presents Iqbal's' optimistic poetic thoughts regarding revitalization of Islam in descriptive and analytical way to explicate the Iqbal's message to the readers.

Keywords: Allama Iqbal, Islamic Education, Iqbal's Philosophy, Muslim Brotherhood.

کلیدی الفاظ: علامہ اقبال، اسلامی علوم، نظریہ اقبال، اسلامی بھائی چارہ۔

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